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Deliverable 20.3

HIGH PRECISION POVERTY MAPS

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Abstract

Estimating economic indicators is crucial for achieving a targeted implementation of welfare policies. However, for such policies to be effective, policy makers must have access to a detailed picture of deprivation that goes beyond aggregate estimates at the country (national) level, extending to finer geographical levels and to other domains of interest, such as specific groups of individuals. In this context, we have estimated the regional distribution of poverty and inequality across several European countries using the most recently available data from European censuses and the EU-SILC household surveys. The main goal of this exercise has been to generate poverty maps (via the so-called 'Empirical Best Prediction' (EBP) approach) with the highest geographical precision that the available data permitted, in as many countries as possible.

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

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1. Introduction

Estimating economic indicators is crucial for achieving a targeted implementation of welfare policies. However, for such policies to be effective, policy makers must have access to a detailed picture of deprivation that goes beyond aggregate estimates at the country (national) level, extending to finer geographical levels and to other domains of interest, such as specific groups of individuals. A comprehensive picture can only be constructed by having access to survey and administrative/census data at appropriate spatial scales that are timely and accurate. One possible solution for obtaining accurate indicators at finer spatial scales is by using small area estimation methodologies. The term ‘small areas’ is typically used to describe domains (e.g. geographic areas) whose sample sizes are not large enough to allow sufficiently precise direct estimation, i.e. estimation that is based only on the sample data from a domain (Rao, 2003). Small area-specific sample sizes often also hamper the use of conventional design-based estimators. In such cases, model-based estimation procedures can be considered for improving the precision of the direct estimates.

Small area estimation is conventionally concerned with the estimation of small area averages and totals. More recently, some of the research effort has been shifted towards methods for estimating poverty (deprivation) indicators at the small area level, also known as poverty mapping. Poverty mapping can offer a detailed description of the spatial distribution of poverty and inequality within a country. It combines individual and household survey data with Census/administrative data with the objective of estimating welfare indicators for geographic areas or domains of interest. In recent years, a range of alternative model based small area methodologies for poverty mapping have been proposed, among which we highlight the so-called Empirical Best Prediction (EBP) model suggested by Molina and Rao (2010).

In this document, we report the joint efforts carried out by the Center for Demographic Studies (CED) in Spain and the Social Statistics Division of the University of Southampton in the United Kingdom to generate poverty maps across European countries. Using the most recently available data from European censuses and the EU-SILC household surveys, the main goal of this exercise has been to generate poverty maps (via the EBP method) with the highest geographical precision that the available data permitted, in as many countries as possible.

The report is organised as follows. In section 2, we briefly describe the key distributional indicators we are interested in (technical details of the estimation techniques are given in the appendix). The country-by-country findings are reported in section 3. Finally, we conclude with some final remarks in section 4.

2. Methodology

Poverty mapping techniques aim at generating reliable poverty and inequality indicators at small area levels. The technical underpinnings of the EBP and other well-known small-area estimation methods are presented in the appendix. In a nutshell, they can be summarised as follows.

1. Because of their relatively small sample size, household surveys with income information typically have few observations at the small administrative levels where we want to generate our poverty or inequality estimates.
2. Since household survey data is insufficient to generate reliable estimates, it is complemented via auxiliary information (typically censuses or administrative registers). The alternative sources of information contain variables correlated with income that are also available in the household survey. These variables are also known as the set of ‘link variables’.
3. Once the different link variables have been identified, they are used as predictors of (log of) income in a model that is run on the household survey data.
4. Using the specifications of the model fitted in the previous step, one generates income estimates based on census or register data. These estimates are used to complement the few observations available from the household surveys and generate more reliable poverty and inequality estimates at small area levels.

Now, we introduce the different poverty and inequality indicators we will report across European regions.

Poverty measures

Assuming we have estimated a distribution of incomes $\{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ with a poverty line z^1 , we can define the following indicators.

Headcount ratio: proportion of individuals below the poverty line. It is calculated as

$$H = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\max \left\{ 0, \frac{z - y_i}{z} \right\} \right)^0 = \frac{q}{n}$$

where q is the number of individuals below the poverty line. Because of its simplicity, it is one of the most standard poverty measures.

Relative Poverty Gap: it is defined as the average of the relative poverty gaps, and is calculated as:

$$P = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\max \left\{ 0, \frac{z - y_i}{z} \right\} \right)$$

The relative poverty gap is also a very popular poverty measure. Basically, it measures the average relative distance of ‘poor incomes’ (i.e. incomes of poor individuals) with respect to the poverty line.

¹ As is common practice in the EU context, we define the poverty line as 60% of the median of the distribution.

Inequality measures

Relative Gini index: it is defined as the average relative distance between any two incomes taken at random. It is calculated as

$$G = \frac{1}{2\mu n^2} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |y_i - y_j|$$

where μ is the average of the distribution. The Gini index is perhaps the most popular inequality index used in empirical analyses. It takes a value of 0 when all incomes are the same and it takes a value of 1 when all income is owned by a single individual.

3. Results: Poverty maps in Europe

In this section, we report the results of the EBP method applied to European countries where data was available. We used two datasets for our analysis: Integrated Public Use Microdata Series (IPUMS) International and EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC).

IPUMS is the world's largest archive of Census microdata (currently 82 countries are included in the database). It is composed of individual records organised into households from population censuses, with sample densities ranging from 1 to 10% of national populations. It provides more geographical detail and bigger sample sizes than the EU-SILC data.

In Table 3.1 samples available for each country and the greatest geographical detail provided in IPUMS are presented. Eight European countries (Austria, Greece, Ireland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain and Switzerland) provide NUTS-3 level geographical information while two countries (France and Italy) provide NUTS-2 and two countries (Germany and the UK) provide only NUTS-1 level geographical detail. Since Hungary and Netherlands do not provide any geographical information (the only geographical information provided is the continent and region of the country), we were not able to include them in our analysis.

Table 3.1 Samples provided by European countries and geographical detail in IPUMS

Countries	Samples	Geographical detail
Austria	1971- 1981- 1991- 2001 - 2011	NUTS-3
France	1962- 1968- 1975- 1982- 1990- 1999- 2006- 2011	NUTS-2
Germany	1970- 1971- 1981 - 1987	NUTS-1
Greece	1971- 1981- 1991 - 2001	NUTS-3
Hungary	1970- 1980- 1990 - 2001	
Ireland	1971- 1979- 1981- 1986- 1991- 1996- 2002- 2006 - 2011	NUTS-3
Italy	2001	NUTS-2
Netherlands	1960- 1971- 2001	
Portugal	1981- 1991- 2001 - 2011	NUTS-3
Romania	1977- 1992 - 2002	NUTS-3
Slovenia	2002	NUTS-3
Spain	1981- 1991- 2001 - 2011	NUTS-3
Switzerland	1970- 1980- 1990 - 200	NUTS-3
UK	1991- 2001	NUTS-1

Source <https://international.ipums.org/international-action/variables/group/h-geog>

While EU-SILC embodies detailed income information, it fails to provide geographical detail in most of the countries. The highest geographical detail available in EU-SILC is at NUTS-2 level. Table 3.2 demonstrates the year of entry of European countries to the EU-SILC database and the geographical detail provided by each country. As shown in Table 3.2, many countries provide geographical information only at NUTS-1 level.

Data are available in both IPUMS and EU-SILC for fourteen countries: Austria, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland and UK. Geographical detail provided in the IPUMS and EU-SILC for these countries is provided in Table 3.3.

Table 3.2 Year of entry of European countries to the EU-SILC and geographical detail provided

Country	Year of Entry	Geographical detail
Belgium	2003	NUTS-1
Bulgaria	2006	NUTS-1
Czech Republic	2005	NUTS-2
Denmark	2003	NUTS-1
Germany	2005	NUTS-1
Estonia	2004	NUTS-1 = NUTS-2
Ireland	2003	NUTS-1
Greece	2003	NUTS-1
Spain	2004	NUTS-2
France	2004	NUTS-2
Italy	2004	NUTS-1
Cyprus	2005	NUTS-1 = NUTS-2 = NUTS-3
Latvia	2005	NUTS-1 = NUTS-2
Lithuania	2005	NUTS-1 = NUTS-2
Luxembourg	2003	NUTS-1 = NUTS-2 = NUTS-3
Hungary	2005	NUTS-1
Malta	2005	NUTS-1 = NUTS-2
Netherlands	2005	NUTS-1
Austria	2003	NUTS-1
Poland	2005	NUTS-1
Portugal	2004	NUTS-1
Romania	2007	NUTS-1
Slovenia	2005	NUTS-1
Slovakia	2005	NUTS-1
Finland	2004	NUTS-2
Sweden	2004	NUTS-1
UK	2005	NUTS-1
Croatia	2010	NUTS-1
Iceland	2004	NUTS-1 = NUTS-2
Turkey	2006	NUTS-1
Norway	2003	NUTS-1
Switzerland	2007	NUTS-1

Table 3.3 Geographical detail provided by the countries present both in EU-SILC and IPUMS

Countries	EU-SILC		IPUMS	
	Year	Geographical Detail	Year	Geographical Detail
Austria	2011	NUTS-1	2011	NUTS-3
France	2011	NUTS-2	2011	NUTS-2
Greece	2004	NUTS-1	2001	NUTS-3
Ireland	2011	NUTS-1	2011	NUTS-3
Italy	2004	NUTS-1	2001	NUTS-2
Portugal	2011	NUTS-0	2011	NUTS-3
Romania	2007	NUTS-1	2002	NUTS-3
Slovenia	2005	NUTS-0	2002	NUTS-3
Spain	2011	NUTS-2	2011	NUTS-3
Switzerland	2008	NUTS-1	2000	NUTS-3
Germany	2004	NUTS-0	1987	NUTS-1
UK	2005	NUTS-2	2001	NUTS-1
Netherlands	2005	NUTS-0	2001	NUTS-0
Hungary	2005	NUTS-1	2001	NUTS-0

We were able to produce poverty estimates (poverty gap, head count ratio and Gini index) for eight countries (Austria, Greece, Ireland, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland) at NUTS-3 level, and for two countries (France and Italy), at NUTS-2 level.

For these ten countries, we used the latest IPUMS samples and those EU-SILC data in comparable timeframe available. We created link variables for each country from the variables common to both datasets in each country, such as number of rooms, availability of toilet, bathroom facilities, car or telephone. In each of the ten countries we included only educational attainment and employment status as individual level variables (being aware of the fact that the list of individual variables can be extended more). Information regarding income is only available in SILC data. We used the already constructed variable (HX090) Equivalised Disposable Income. HX090 is a constructed from total disposable household income using within household non-response inflation factor and equivalised household size.

Neither Netherlands nor Hungary provides geographical detail in IPUMS (Only NUTS-0 level is available) while Germany and UK provide only NUTS-1 level information. Netherlands was excluded from the analysis (only NUTS-0 level information both in IPUMS and EU-SILC). Hungary and UK were also excluded since EU-SILC provides more detailed geographical information than IPUMS and hence there is no need to apply EBP methods. Germany is also excluded since the IPUMS sample is from 1987 that it would not be comparable with the SILC data from 2004.

3.1 Spain

Data sources: Census year 2011, EU-SILC year 2011.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Telephone availability

From SILC we used the HS070 variable to create the telephone availability variable, which is a household level variable asked to the household respondent. In the variable HS070 'Do you have a telephone (including mobile phone)?' is asked and it has 3 categories: (1) Yes, (2) No, but would like to have it but cannot afford, (3) No, not have one for other reasons, e.g. do not want or do not

need. We merged the categories (2) No, but would like to have it but cannot afford, (3) No, not have one for other reasons and recoded as (0) No and kept (1) as Yes.

The variable regarding the availability of a telephone in the dwelling in the IPUMS data (PHONE) refers only to the existence of telephone lines, mobile phones are excluded. It is coded as (0) Not in universe, (1) No and (2) Yes. The universe for Spain in 2011 is defined as buildings mainly or exclusively as dwellings. Since there is no other variable in the IPUMS data providing information about the existence of a mobile phone in the household, we used this variable to create this link variable regarding telephone availability. In the IPUMS data, we first dropped the observations which fall in the category 'Not in universe' and recoded 'No' as (0) and 'Yes' as (1).

The *telephone availability* variable common in two datasets has the two categories: (0) No and (1) Yes.

- Var2: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. However, unlike the SILC data, kitchens are included in the IPUMS sample for Spain in 2011. This variable is coded from 1 to 25, indicating the exact number of rooms in the dwelling of the household. To make it compatible with the categories of HH030 in SILC, we recoded the ROOMS variable in IPUMS, pooling all the categories 6 and higher under one category (6) to indicate dwellings with six or more rooms.

While ROOMS in IPUMS includes kitchens, HH030 in SILC excludes them (unless the space for cooking is used for other purposes as well like dining). In the case of Spain, neither of the datasets includes a variable specifying the existence of a kitchen, so we are not able to distinguish more with respect to kitchens.

The unique *number of rooms* variable has the following categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var3: Tenure status

We used HH021 which shows the tenure status of the household with these categories: (1) Outright owner, (2) Owner paying mortgage, (3) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (4) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate, (5) Accommodation is provided free. We merged the categories (1) Outright owner and (2) Owner paying mortgage of the HH021 variable and recoded it as (1) referring to being an 'Owner' and recoded all the rest of the categories (Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate and Accommodation is provided free) as (0) referring to 'Not owner'.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for the tenure status which only distinguishes between (1) Owned and (2) Not owned. Household with mortgage payments or with other lending arrangements are considered as owning the dwelling even if they have not completed all the repayments. We recoded 'Not owned' as (0).

The unique *tenure status* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var4: Toilet availability

We used HH091 from the SILC data to create the variable regarding the availability of toilet. HH091 asks the question: 'Is there an indoor flushing toilet in the dwelling?' and has 3 categories: (1) Yes, for sole use of the household, (2) Yes, shared and (3) No. We recoded (3) No as (0) and pooled together (1) Yes, for sole use of the household and (2) Yes, shared under the category (1) referring to 'Yes'.

IPUMS has a variable called TOILET with two categories: (10) No toilet, (20) Have toilet, type not specified. This variable in some countries distinguishes between having an access to a flush toilet

or other type of installation. But in the case of Spain, this information is not available. The variable only provides us with the information regarding the presence or absence of toilet facilities. We recoded (10) No toilet as (0) and (20) Have toilet as (1).

We created a unique *toilet availability* variable in two datasets with the categories: (0) No toilet and (1) Yes, has a toilet.

- Var5: Bathroom availability

To create the variable for the availability of bathroom facilities we used the variable HH080 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has proper room with a bath or a shower and it is coded in 3 categories (1) Yes, for sole use of the household, (2) Shared, (3) No. We recoded (3) No as (0) and pooled together (1) Yes, for sole use of the household and (2) Yes, shared under the category (1) referring to 'Yes'.

IPUMS's BATH variable indicating if the household has access to bathing facilities and has only two categories: (1) No bathing facility, (2) Yes, have bathing facility, exclusivity not specified. We recoded (1) No bathing facility as (0) and (2) Yes, have bathing facility as (1).

The unique *bathroom availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No bathing facility and (1) Yes, with a bathing facility.

- Var6: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 (Highest ISCED level attained) from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. We added persons who have never been to education (coded -2 in the flag variable) under category (1). So, category (1) now comprises of individuals with less than primary education together with individuals who have completed primary education. We pooled all the individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which indicates the highest level of schooling completed. The universe for this variable is also defined as persons aged 16 and older. It has these following categories: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (20) Primary (first stage of basic education), (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed. Individuals under 16 are classified under the category (0) Not in universe. We merged the categories Less than primary and Primary (first stage of basic education) under category (1) referring to Less than primary or primary education completed. We recoded Lower secondary education as (2), Upper secondary as (3), Post-secondary non-tertiary education as (4) and University completed as (5).

Education variable common to two datasets has the categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16, (1) Less than primary or primary education completed, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) Tertiary education.

- Var7: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable, which has the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive. The universe of this variable is also individuals 16 and over. We recoded EMPSTAT variable in the IPUMS data, gathering individuals younger than

16 under the category (0) as well. New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

We created a unique *employment* variable in two datasets with the categories: (0) Not in the universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

We chose to exclude the households with negative equivalised disposable income from our calculations, which led us to drop around 1% of the total sample in Spain.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets:

Income \sim Phone availability + Number of rooms + Tenure status + Toilet availability + Bathroom availability + Education + Employment

For Spain in 2011, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (52 regions). But the SILC data has no geographical identifier at NUTS-3 level. SILC provides us only with NUTS-2 level geographical identifiers. Therefore, due to this lack of geographical detail at NUTS-3 level in SILC data, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.4 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Spain, year 2011

ENUTS-3 Region	H	P	G
A Coruña	0.25	0.14	0.37
Lugo	0.26	0.15	0.37
Ourense	0.27	0.15	0.38
Pontevedra	0.26	0.14	0.37
Asturias	0.26	0.14	0.37
Cantabria	0.25	0.14	0.37
Alava	0.23	0.13	0.36
Guipuzcoa	0.24	0.13	0.36
Vizcaya	0.24	0.13	0.36
Navarra	0.24	0.13	0.36
Rioja	0.25	0.14	0.37
Huesca	0.25	0.14	0.37
Teruel	0.27	0.15	0.38
Zaragoza	0.25	0.13	0.37
Madrid	0.24	0.13	0.36
Avila	0.27	0.15	0.38
Burgos	0.25	0.14	0.37
Leon	0.26	0.15	0.37
Palencia	0.25	0.14	0.37
Salamanca	0.27	0.15	0.38
Segovia	0.25	0.14	0.37
Soria	0.26	0.14	0.37
Valladolid	0.25	0.13	0.37
Zamora	0.27	0.15	0.38
Albacete	0.26	0.14	0.37
Ciudad Real	0.26	0.14	0.37
Cuenca	0.27	0.15	0.38
Guadalajara	0.25	0.14	0.37
Toledo	0.26	0.14	0.37
Badajoz	0.27	0.15	0.38
Caceres	0.27	0.15	0.38
Barcelona	0.25	0.14	0.37
Girona	0.26	0.14	0.37
Lleida	0.25	0.14	0.37
Tarragona	0.25	0.14	0.37
Alicante	0.25	0.14	0.37
Castellon	0.26	0.14	0.37
Valencia	0.25	0.14	0.37
Illes Balears	0.26	0.15	0.37
Almeria	0.26	0.14	0.37
Cadiz	0.26	0.15	0.38
Cordoba	0.26	0.14	0.37
Granada	0.25	0.14	0.37
Huelva	0.27	0.15	0.38
Jaen	0.26	0.14	0.37
Malaga	0.26	0.15	0.37
Sevilla	0.26	0.14	0.37
Murcia	0.25	0.14	0.37
Ceuta	0.30	0.18	0.40
Melilla	0.28	0.16	0.39
Palmas	0.28	0.16	0.38
Tenerife	0.28	0.16	0.38

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.1 Spanish NUTS-3 regions

Source <http://www.cerebriti.com/uploads/2495106cf29662cf48f02b91af3a79bc.jpg>

Figure 3.2 Headcount ratio estimates for Spanish regions, year 2011. Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.3 Poverty Gap estimates for Spanish regions, year 2011. Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.4 Gini coefficient estimates for Spanish regions, year 2011. Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.2 Portugal

Data sources: Census year 2011, EU-SILC year 2011.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. Likewise SILC data, kitchens are excluded in the IPUMS sample for Portugal in 2011. This variable is coded from (1) to (10) indicating number of rooms occupied by the household and (99) Not in universe. Universe is defined as private dwellings. We pooled all the categories greater 6 together (including 6) under the category (6) referring to 'Six or more rooms'.

The unique *number of rooms* variable has the following categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var2: Tenure status

We used HH021, which shows the tenure status of the household with these categories: (1) Outright owner, (2) Owner paying mortgage, (3) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (4) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate, (5) Accommodation is provided free. We merged the categories (1) Outright owner and (2) Owner paying mortgage of the HH021 variable and recoded it as (1) referring to being an 'Owner' and recoded all the rest of the categories (Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate and Accommodation is provided free) as (0) referring to 'Not owner'.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for the tenure status which only distinguishes between (1) Owned and (2) Not owned and has the category (0) to refer to 'not in universe'. Universe is defined as conventional dwellings in conventional dwellings of usual residence. Households with mortgage payments or with other lending arrangements are considered as owning the dwelling even if they have not completed all the repayments. We dropped the observations not in the universe from the sample (Around 1.4% of the total sample) and recoded 'Not owned' as (0).

The unique *tenure status* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var3: Toilet availability

We used HH091 from the SILC data to create the variable regarding the availability of toilet. HH091 asks the question: 'Is there an indoor flushing toilet in the dwelling?' and has 3 categories: (1) Yes, for sole use of the household, (2) Yes, shared and (3) No. We recoded (3) No as (0). Since there is no information regarding the exclusive use of the toilet facility in the IPUMS data, we pooled together (1) Yes, for sole use of the household and (2) Yes, shared under the category (1) referring to 'Yes there is a flush toilet'.

IPUMS has a variable called TOILET with these categories: (0) Not in universe, (10) No toilet, (20) Have toilet, type not specified, (21) Flush toilet, (22) Non-flush, latrine. This variable distinguishes between having an access to a flush toilet or other type of installation in the Portugal sample, but doesn't provide information regarding the exclusive use of the toilet facility. We first dropped the observations not in universe (Around 1.2% of the total sample). We recoded (21) Flush toilet as (1) and pooled together all other categories as under (0) referring to 'No flush toilet'.

We created a unique *toilet availability* variable in two datasets with the categories: (0) No flush toilet and (1) Yes, has a flush toilet.

- Var4: Bathroom availability

To create the variable for the availability of bathroom facilities, we used the variable HH081 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has proper room with a bath or a shower and it is coded in 3 categories (1) Yes, for sole use of the household, (2) Shared, (3) No. We recoded (3) No as (0) and pooled together (1) Yes, for sole use of the household and (2) Yes, shared under the category (1) referring to 'Yes'.

IPUMS's BATH variable indicating if the household has access to bathing facilities and has these categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) No bathing facility, (2) Yes, have bathing facility, exclusivity not specified. After dropping the observations 'Not in universe', we recoded (1) No bathing facility as (0) and (2) Yes, have bathing facility as (1).

The unique *bathroom availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No bathing facility and (1) Yes, with a bathing facility.

- Var5: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 (Highest ISCED level attained) from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. We recoded persons who have never been to education (coded -2 in the flag variable) under category a new category (0). We also put individuals younger than 16 under this category.

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which indicates the highest level of schooling completed. The universe for this variable is defined as all persons in Portugal. It has these following categories: (10) Less than primary, (20) Primary (first stage of basic education), (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed. We pool all the individuals younger than 16 and Less than primary education under the category (0). We recode Primary education as (1), Lower secondary education as (2), Upper secondary as (3), Post-secondary non-tertiary education as (4) and University completed as (5).

Education variable common to two datasets has the categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16 and individuals less than primary education, (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education and (5) Tertiary education.

- Var6: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable which has the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive. The universe of this variable is individuals 15 and over in Portugal. We recoded EMPSTAT variable in the IPUMS data, gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets:

Income ~ Number of rooms + Tenure status + Toilet availability + Bathroom availability + Education + Employment

For Portugal in 2011, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (22 regions). But the SILC data has no geographical identifiers. Hence, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.5 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Portugal, year 2011

NUTS-3 Region	H	P	G
Minho-Lima	0.198	0.052	0.352
Cávado	0.184	0.048	0.353
Ave	0.207	0.055	0.352
Grande Porto	0.198	0.053	0.364
Tâmega	0.219	0.059	0.346
Entre Douro e Vouga	0.200	0.053	0.352
Douro	0.205	0.055	0.356
Alto Trás-os-Montes	0.204	0.054	0.356
Algarve	0.201	0.054	0.356
Baixo Vouga	0.186	0.048	0.355
Baixo Mondego	0.176	0.046	0.362
Pinhal Litoral	0.182	0.047	0.355
Dão-Lafões	0.194	0.051	0.355
Oeste	0.199	0.053	0.354
Médio Tejo	0.195	0.051	0.355
Pinhal Interior Norte/Pinhal Interior Sul/Serra da Estrela/Beira Interior Norte/Beira Interior Sul/Cova da Beira	0.206	0.055	0.354
Grande Lisboa	0.185	0.049	0.365
Península de Setúbal	0.193	0.051	0.359
Lezíria do Tejo	0.204	0.055	0.357
Alentejo Litoral/Alto Alentejo/Alentejo Central/Baixo Alentejo	0.211	0.057	0.357
Região Autónoma dos Açores	0.201	0.053	0.351
Região Autónoma da Madeira	0.207	0.055	0.355

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.5 Portuguese NUTS-3 regions

Source: DRAPC (<http://www.drapc.min-agricultura.pt/images/documentos/nuts3.jpg>)

Figure 3.6 Headcount ratio estimates for Portuguese regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.7 Poverty Gap estimates for Portuguese regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.8 Gini coefficient estimates for Portuguese regions, year 2011.

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.3 Austria

Data sources: Census year 2011, EU-SILC year 2011.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes. To make it compatible with the categories of ROOMS in the IPUMS sample, we pooled together the categories (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms and (5) Five rooms under the category (4) to refer to 'Three to five rooms'.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. Likewise SILC data, kitchens are excluded in the IPUMS sample for Austria in 2011. This variable is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (4) Three to five rooms, (6) Six or more rooms.

The unique *number of rooms* variable has the following categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (4) Three to five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var2: Tenure status

We used HH021 which shows the tenure status of the household with these categories: (1) Outright owner, (2) Owner paying mortgage, (3) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (4) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate, (5) Accommodation is provided free. We merged the categories (1) Outright owner and (2) Owner paying mortgage of the HH021 variable and recoded it as (1) referring to being an 'Owner' and recoded all the rest of the categories (Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate and Accommodation is provided free) as (0) referring to 'Not owner'.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for the tenure status which only distinguishes between (1) Owned and (2) Not owned and has the category (0) to refer to 'not in universe'. Universe is defined as conventional dwellings. Households with mortgage payments or with other lending

arrangements are considered as owning the dwelling even if they have not completed all the repayments. We dropped the observations not in the universe from the sample (Around 1.5% of the total sample) and recoded 'Not owned' as (0).

The unique *tenure status* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var3: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 (Highest ISCED level attained) from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. We added persons who have never been to education (coded -2 in the flag variable) under category (1). So, category (1) now comprises of individuals with less than primary education together with individuals who have completed primary education. We have all the individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which indicates the highest level of schooling completed. The universe for this variable is defined as persons aged 15 and older. It has these following categories: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (20) Primary (first stage of basic education), (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed. We pool all the individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) Not in universe. We merged the categories Less than primary and Primary (first stage of basic education) under category (1) referring to Less than primary or primary education completed. We recoded Lower secondary education as (2), Upper secondary as (3), Post-secondary non-tertiary education as (4) and University completed as (5).

Education variable common to two datasets has the categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16, (1) Less than primary or primary education completed, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) Tertiary education.

- Var4: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable, which has the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive. The universe of this variable is individuals 15 and over. We recoded EMPSTAT variable in the IPUMS data, gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets:

Income ~ Number of rooms + Tenure status + Education + Employment

For Austria in 2011, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (31 regions). But the SILC data has no geographical identifier at NUTS-3 level. SILC provides us only with NUTS-1 level geographical identifiers. Therefore, due to this lack of geographical detail at NUTS-3 level in SILC data, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.6 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Austria, year 2011

ENUTS-3 Region	H	P	G
Mittelburgenland	0.183	0.045	0.321
Nordburgenland	0.181	0.045	0.322
Mostviertel-Eisenwurzen	0.178	0.044	0.321
Niederösterreich-Süd	0.197	0.050	0.323
Sankt Pölten	0.190	0.048	0.323
Waldviertel	0.183	0.046	0.322
Weinviertel	0.175	0.043	0.320
Wiener Umland/Nordteil	0.172	0.042	0.321
Wiener Umland/Südteil	0.187	0.047	0.323
Wien	0.246	0.065	0.322
Klagenfurt-Villach	0.200	0.051	0.324
Oberkärnten	0.189	0.048	0.322
Unterkärnten	0.190	0.048	0.322
Graz	0.198	0.050	0.324
Liezen	0.191	0.048	0.322
Östliche Obersteiermark	0.214	0.056	0.324
Oststeiermark	0.177	0.044	0.321
West- und Südsteiermark	0.185	0.046	0.322
Westliche Obersteiermark	0.196	0.050	0.323
Innviertel	0.182	0.046	0.323
Linz-Wels	0.206	0.053	0.325
Mühlviertel	0.179	0.045	0.323
Steyr-Kirchdorf	0.198	0.051	0.325
Traunviertel	0.186	0.047	0.323
Lungau	0.193	0.049	0.322
Salzburg und Umgebung	0.201	0.051	0.324
Außerfern	0.189	0.047	0.321
Innsbruck	0.205	0.053	0.324
Osttirol	0.192	0.048	0.321
Bludenz-Bregenzener Wald	0.191	0.048	0.322
Rheintal-Bodenseegebiet	0.199	0.051	0.324

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.9 Austrian NUTS-3 regions

Source: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/9/91/%C3%96sterreich_-_NUTS1,_NUTS2,_NUTS3.png

Figure 3.10 Headcount ratio estimates for Austrian regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.11 Poverty Gap estimates for Austrian regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.12 Gini coefficient estimates for Austrian regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.4 Ireland

Data sources: Census year 2011, EU-SILC year 2011.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. Likewise SILC data, kitchens are excluded in the IPUMS sample for Ireland in 2011. This variable is coded from (1) to (9) indicating number of rooms occupied by the household, (98) to refer to 'Unknown' and (99) to 'Not in universe'. Universe is defined as private households. We dropped the unknown and not in the universe observations and pooled all the categories greater than 6 together (including 6) under the category (6) referring to 'Six or more rooms'.

The unique *number of rooms* variable has the following categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var2: Tenure status

We used HH021 which shows the tenure status of the household with these categories: (1) Outright owner, (2) Owner paying mortgage, (3) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (4) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate, (5) Accommodation is provided free. We merged the categories (1) Outright owner and (2) Owner paying mortgage and recoded it as (1) referring to being an 'Owner' and pooled together all the rest of the categories (Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate and Accommodation is provided free) and recoded as (0) referring to 'Not owner'.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for the tenure status which only distinguishes between (1) Owned and (2) Not owned and has the category (0) to refer to 'not in universe'. Universe is defined as private households. Households with mortgage payments or with other lending arrangements are considered as owning the dwelling even if they have not completed all the repayments. We dropped the observations not in the universe from the sample (Around 3% of the total sample) and recoded 'Not owned' as (0).

The unique *tenure status* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var3: Computer availability

We used HS090 which shows whether the household has a computer or not and if not either because it cannot afford it or for other reasons. It has the following categories: (1) Yes, (2) No, cannot afford and (3) No, other reason. We pooled together No (cannot afford) and No (other reason) together and recoded as (0) No, without specifying the reason for not owning one to make it compatible with IPUMS.

IPUMS has a variable named COMPUTER indicating if the household has a personal computer. This variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) No, (2) Yes and (9) Unknown/missing. Universe is defined as private households. We first dropped the not in universe and unknown/missing observations and then recoded Yes as (1) and No as (0).

We created a unique *computer availability* variable in two datasets with the categories: (0) No, does not have a computer and (1) Yes, has a computer.

- Var4: Car availability

To create the variable for the car availability, we used the variable HS110 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has a car or not and if not whether because it cannot afford it or for other reasons. It is coded in 3 categories (1) Yes (2) No, cannot afford it (3) No, other reason. We pooled together No (cannot afford) and No (other reason) together and recoded as (0) No, without specifying the reason for not owning one to make it compatible with IPUMS.

IPUMS's AUTOS variable indicating if a member of the household owned or had use of a vehicle and has these categories: (0) No autos, (1) One auto, (2) Two autos, (3) Three autos, (4) Four autos, (8) Unknown and (9) Not in universe. Universe is defined as private households. Top-code (4) Four autos refers to four or more cars. AUTOS variable does not provide us information regarding the reasons for not owning a car (whether because cannot afford or for other reasons e.g. do not need) but provides information regarding the number of cars owned by the household. We first dropped the observations 'Unknown' and 'Not in universe'. In order to make it compatible with SILC (HS110 does not provide information about the number of cars owned), we pooled together the categories (1) One auto, (2) Two autos, (3) Three autos and (4) Four autos and recoded as (1) referring to 'Yes, has a car'.

The unique *car availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No, does not have a car and (1) Yes, has a car.

- Var5: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 (Highest ISCED level attained) from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. We recoded persons who have never been to education (coded -2 in the flag variable) under category a new category (0). We also put individuals younger than 16 under this category.

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which indicates the highest level of schooling completed. The universe for this variable is defined as present persons age 15 and more in Ireland. It has these following categories: (0) Not in universe, (20) Primary (first stage of basic education), (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed and (99) Unknown/missing. In Ireland, it is stated that Primary education is overestimated since (20) Primary education includes persons with no formal education as well. We drop the observations which are Unknown/missing (Around 3% of the total sample). We then pool all the individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) like in SILC. We recode Primary education as (1), Lower secondary education as (2), Upper secondary as (3), Post-secondary non-tertiary education as (4) and University completed as (5).

Education variable common to two datasets has the categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16, (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education and (5) Tertiary education.

- Var6: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person. We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable which has the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive. The universe of this variable is non-absent persons 15 and over in Ireland. We recoded EMPSTAT variable in the IPUMS data, gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets:

Income ~ Number of rooms + Tenure status + Computer availability + Car availability + Education + Employment

For Ireland in 2011, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (8 regions). But the SILC data has no geographical identifiers. Hence, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.7 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Ireland, year 2011

ENUTS-3 Region	H	P	G
Border Region	0.176	0.044	0.317
Midlands Region	0.175	0.043	0.317
West Region	0.168	0.041	0.316
Dublin Region	0.184	0.046	0.321
Mid-East Region	0.157	0.038	0.315
Mid-West Region	0.171	0.042	0.318
South-East Region	0.176	0.044	0.317
South-West Region	0.172	0.043	0.317

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.13 Irish NUTS-3 regions

Source: <http://www.discoveringireland.com/images/stories/regions.gif>

Figure 3.14 Headcount ratio estimates for Irish regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.15 Poverty Gap estimates for Irish regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.16 Gini coefficient estimates for Irish regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.5 Romania

Data sources: Census year 2002, EU-SILC year 2007.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. In the IPUMS data, kitchens are also excluded in Romania in 2002 sample. This variable is coded from (1) One room to (12) Twelve or more rooms. Universe is defined as all households. We aggregated all the categories greater than 6 (Including 6) and recoded as (6) to refer to 'Six or more rooms'.

The unique *number of rooms* variable in two datasets has the categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms and (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var2: Toilet availability

We used HH090 from the SILC data to create the variable regarding the availability of toilet. HH090 asks the question: 'Is there an indoor flushing toilet for sole use of the household?' and the answers are coded under two categories: (1) Yes and (2) No. We recoded this variable by changing (2) No to (0).

The variable for the presence of a toilet in the household (TOILET) in the IPUMS data distinguishes between the absence and presence of a flushing toilet and has these two categories: (11) No, flush toilet and (21) Yes, Flush toilet. However, no specification is made regarding the exclusivity of access to the toilet facilities. Universe is defined as all households. We recoded (21) Yes, Flush toilet as (1) and (11) No, flush toilet as (0).

The unique *toilet availability* variable created in two datasets has the categories: (0) No flush toilet and (1) Yes, has flush a toilet.

- Var3: Bathroom availability

To create the variable for the availability of bathroom facilities we used the variable HH080 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has a proper room with a bath or a shower and it is coded in 2 categories (1) Yes, (2) No. We recoded (2) No as (0).

IPUMS's BATH variable indicating if the household has access to bathing facilities has these two categories: (1) No bathing facility, (2) Yes, have bathing facility, exclusivity not specified. Universe is defined as all households. We then recoded (1) No bathing facility as (0) and (2) Yes, have bathing facility as (1).

The unique *bathroom availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No bathing facility and (1) Yes, with a bathing facility.

- Var4: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. We recoded PE040 by pooling all individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which also indicates the highest level of schooling completed. Universe for this variable is defined as persons aged 6 and older in Romania.

It has these following categories: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed and (99) Unknown/missing. We first dropped the unknown/missing observations (Around 1.3% of the total sample). Romania has a 4-4-4 educational system and 4-year primary level is coded as 'Less than primary' and the next degree 8-year is coded as 'Lower secondary'. No 'Primary education' can be identified in the Romanian sample. Therefore, we recoded Less than Primary as (1), Lower secondary as (2), Upper secondary as (3), Post-secondary non-tertiary as (4) and University completed as (5). We pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

The unique *education* variable in two datasets has these categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16, (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education and (5) Tertiary education.

- Var5: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person. We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable to create the employment variable with the categories: (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed, (3) Inactive. Universe of this variable is all persons. We pooled all individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

We chose to exclude the households with negative equivalised disposable income from our calculations, which led us to drop around 3% of the total sample in Romania.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets.

The model we fitted for Romania is:

Income ~ Number of rooms + Toilet availability + Bathroom availability + Education + Employment

For Romania in 2002, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (42 regions). But the SILC data has no geographical identifier at NUTS-3 level. Due to this lack of geographical detail in SILC data, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.8 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Romania, year 2007

	H	P	G
Bistrita Nasaud	0.277	0.132	0.378
Cluj	0.3	0.142	0.381
Maramures	0.214	0.098	0.354
Satu Mare	0.292	0.139	0.38
Salaj	0.292	0.139	0.381
Salaj	0.322	0.157	0.392
Alba	0.284	0.135	0.38
Brasov	0.181	0.078	0.335
Covasna	0.279	0.135	0.378
Harghita	0.266	0.125	0.37
Mures	0.283	0.137	0.381
Sibiu	0.23	0.105	0.358
Bacau	0.305	0.144	0.382
Botosani	0.348	0.17	0.395
Iasi	0.298	0.142	0.386
Neamt	0.323	0.156	0.39
Suceava	0.342	0.166	0.395
Vaslui	0.355	0.174	0.397
Braila	0.285	0.133	0.375
Buzau	0.345	0.169	0.397
Constanta	0.212	0.094	0.349
Galati	0.268	0.124	0.369
Tulcea	0.305	0.143	0.379
Vrancea	0.324	0.155	0.388
Arges	0.276	0.13	0.377
Calarasi	0.358	0.175	0.396
Dimbovita	0.318	0.151	0.385
Giurgiu	0.363	0.178	0.396
Ialomita	0.357	0.176	0.4
Prahova	0.273	0.128	0.376
Teleorman	0.361	0.178	0.399
Bucuresti	0.116	0.043	0.304
Ilfov	0.321	0.152	0.384
Dolj	0.291	0.137	0.38
Gorj	0.298	0.141	0.379
Mehedinti	0.311	0.149	0.386
Olt	0.337	0.162	0.39
Valcea	0.322	0.156	0.393
Arad	0.277	0.131	0.377
Caras Severin	0.274	0.128	0.371
Hunedoara	0.204	0.089	0.342
Timis	0.223	0.099	0.354

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.17 Romanian NUTS-3 regions

Source: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/8/8d/Romanian_license_plate_codes.png

Figure 3.18 Headcount ratio estimates for Romanian regions, year 2007

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.19 Poverty Gap estimates for Romanian regions, year 2007

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.20 Gini coefficient estimates for Romanian regions, year 2007

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.6 Greece

Data sources: Census year 2001, EU-SILC year 2004.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. Kitchens are excluded in Greece 2001 sample. This variable is coded (1) to (12) indicating the number of rooms and (99) Not in universe. Universe is defined as regular dwellings. We dropped the observations 'Not in universe' (less than 0.4% of the total sample) and gathered together the categories 6 to 12 under the category (6) to refer to 'Six or more rooms'.

The unique *number of rooms* variable in two datasets has the categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six and more rooms.

- Var2: Tenure status

We used HH020 which shows the tenure status of the household with the categories: (1) Owner, (2) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (3) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate (lower price than the market price), (4) Accommodation is provided free. An individual is considered as owner if he possesses a title deed even if the house is fully paid or not. We recoded HH020 pooling together (2) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (3) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate (lower price than the market price), (4) Accommodation is provided free, under (0) Not owned.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for tenure status with the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Owned, (2) Not owned. Universe is defined as private households living in a dwelling. Household with mortgage payments are considered as owning the dwelling even if they have not completed all the repayments. We dropped the observations with (0) Not in universe (less than 0.4 % of the total sample) and recoded (2) Not owned as (0).

The final *tenure status* variable we created in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var3: Toilet availability

We used HH090 from the SILC data which indicates the availability of an indoor flushing toilet for sole use of household. It is coded under two categories: (1) Yes and (2) No. We recoded this variable by changing (2) No to (0).

The variable for the presence of a toilet in the household (TOILET) in the IPUMS data distinguishes between the absence and presence of a flushing toilet and has these categories: (0) Not in universe, (10) No toilet, (21) Flush toilet, (23) Non-flush, other and unspecified (99) Unknown. Universe is defined as occupied private households. We recoded TOILET variable by first dropping the observations with (0) Not in universe, which make up less than 0.4% of the total sample. We then recoded (21) Flush toilet as (1) referring to 'Presence of flushing toilet' and pooled together (10) 'No toilet' and (23) 'Other and unspecified (Not flush) type of toilet' under (0) referring to 'Absence flushing toilet'.

The unique *toilet availability* variable created in two datasets has the categories: (0) No flush toilet and (1) Yes, has a toilet.

- Var4: Bathroom availability

To create the variable for the availability of bathroom facilities, we used the variable HH080 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has a proper room with a bath or a shower and it is coded in 2 categories (1) Yes, (2) No. No specification is made regarding exclusivity of the bathroom. We recoded (2) No as (0).

IPUMS's BATH variable indicating if the household has access to bathing facilities has the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) No bathing facility, (3) Yes, have bathing facility, exclusive use, (4) Yes, have bathing facility, shared use. Universe is defined as regular households. We recoded BATH variable by first dropping the observations with (0) Not in universe, which make up less than 0.4% of the total sample. We then pooled (3) Yes, have bathing facility, exclusive use and (4) Yes, have bathing facility, shared use under the category (1) referring to 'Yes, have bathing facility' and recoded (1) No bathing facility as (0).

The unique *bathroom availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No bathing facility and (1) Yes, with a bathing facility.

- Var5: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary

education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. Persons who have never been to the education (illiterates) are coded as (-2) in the flag variable. We recoded PE040 by aggregating individuals who have never been to education (which could be identified using the flag variable) and individuals younger than 16, under the category (0) referring to 'Less than primary'.

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which also indicates the highest level of schooling completed. Universe for this variable is defined as persons born before 1995 in Greece. It has these following categories: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (20) Primary (first stage of basic education), (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed. We recoded EDATTAIN variable by aggregating Less than primary and individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) referring to 'Less than primary'. We recoded Primary education as (1), Lower secondary education as (2), Upper secondary education as (3), Post-secondary non-tertiary education as (4) and University completed as (5).

The unique *education* variable in two datasets has these categories: (0) Less than primary education (which includes individuals with only pre-primary education, individuals who have never been to education and all the individuals younger than 16), (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) Tertiary education.

- Var6: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person. We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable to create the employment variable with the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed, (3) Inactive. Universe of this variable is defined as persons born before 1991 in Greece. We recoded EMPSTAT variable by gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) to make it compatible with SILC.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

We chose to exclude the households with negative equivalised disposable income from our calculations, which led us to drop around 1% of the total sample in Greece.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets.

The model we fitted for Greece is:

Income ~ Number of rooms + Tenure status + Toilet availability + Bathroom availability + Education + Employment

For Greece in 2001, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (51 regions). But the SILC data has no geographical identifier at NUTS-3 level. SILC provides us only with NUTS-1 level geographical identifiers. Therefore, due to this lack of geographical detail at NUTS-3 level in SILC data, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.9 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Greece, year 2004

ENUTS-3 Region	H	P	G
Evros	0.238	0.066	0.340
Xanthi	0.254	0.071	0.337
Rodopi	0.273	0.079	0.342
Drama	0.226	0.061	0.336
Kavala	0.226	0.061	0.336
Imathia	0.223	0.060	0.335
Thessaloniki	0.202	0.053	0.336
Kilkis	0.231	0.062	0.334
Pella	0.231	0.062	0.334
Picria	0.219	0.058	0.335
Serres	0.239	0.065	0.336
Chalkidiki and Aghion Oros	0.231	0.062	0.334
Grevena	0.242	0.066	0.337
Kastoria	0.224	0.060	0.335
Kozani	0.220	0.059	0.335
Florina	0.226	0.060	0.334
Karditsa	0.239	0.065	0.337
Larissa	0.215	0.057	0.337
Magnissia	0.218	0.058	0.337
Trikala	0.235	0.065	0.338
Arta	0.250	0.069	0.337
Thesprotia	0.241	0.066	0.334
Ioannina	0.227	0.062	0.339
Preveza	0.235	0.064	0.336
Zakynthos	0.226	0.061	0.333
Kerkyra	0.229	0.062	0.335
Kefallinia	0.217	0.058	0.335
Lefkada	0.235	0.065	0.340
Etolia and Akarnania	0.240	0.066	0.335
Achaia	0.212	0.056	0.335
Ilia	0.232	0.063	0.332
Viotia	0.227	0.061	0.335
Evia	0.225	0.060	0.336
Evrytania	0.262	0.074	0.339
Fthiotida	0.224	0.060	0.336
Fokida	0.226	0.062	0.340
Argolida	0.217	0.058	0.335
Arkadia	0.232	0.063	0.337
Korinthia	0.209	0.055	0.333
Lakonia	0.230	0.062	0.334
Messinia	0.228	0.061	0.335
Attiki	0.192	0.050	0.338
Lesvos	0.239	0.066	0.336
Samos	0.235	0.064	0.336
Chios	0.217	0.058	0.335
Dodekanissos	0.218	0.058	0.335
Kyklades	0.234	0.064	0.336
Iraklio	0.221	0.060	0.337
Lassithi	0.234	0.064	0.338
Rethymno	0.220	0.058	0.333
Chania	0.212	0.056	0.335

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.21 Headcount ratio estimates for Greek regions, year 2004

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.22 Poverty Gap estimates for Greek regions, year 2004

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.23 Gini coefficient estimates for Greek regions, year 2004

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.7 Italy

Data sources: Census year 2001, EU-SILC year 2004.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes. We aggregated categories (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms and created a new category: (4) Four or more rooms.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. In the IPUMS data, kitchens are also excluded in Italy in 2001. This variable is coded as: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four or more rooms, (98) Unknown, (99) Not in universe. Universe is defined as private households living in a dwelling. We dropped the observations with (98) Unknown and (99) Not in universe (less than 1% of the total sample).

The unique *number of rooms* variable in two datasets has the categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms and (4) Four or more rooms.

- Var2: Tenure status

We used HH020 which shows the tenure status of the household with the categories: (1) Owner, (2) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (3) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate (lower price than the market price), (4) Accommodation is provided free. An individual is considered as owner if he possesses a title deed even if the house is fully paid or not. We recoded HH020 pooling together (2) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (3) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate (lower price than the market price), (4) Accommodation is provided free, under (0) Not owned.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for tenure status with the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Owned, (2) Not owned and (9) Unknown. Universe is defined as private households living in a dwelling. Household with mortgage payments are considered as owning the dwelling

even if they have not completed all the repayments. We dropped the observations with (0) Not in universe and (9) Unknown (less than 1% of the total sample) and recoded (2) Not owned to (0). The final *tenure status* variable we created in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var3: Toilet availability

We used HH090 from the SILC data to create the variable regarding the availability of toilet. HH090 asks the question: ‘Is there an indoor flushing toilet for sole use of the household?’ and the answers are coded under two categories: (1) Yes and (2) No. We recoded this variable by changing (2) No to (0).

The variable for the presence of a toilet in the household (TOILET) in the IPUMS data distinguishes between the absence and presence of a flushing toilet and has these categories: (0) Not in universe, (11) No, flush toilet, (21) Flush toilet, (99) Unknown. However, no specification is made regarding the exclusivity of access to the toilet facilities. Universe is defined as not hotel or public housing units. We recoded TOILET variable by first dropping the observations with (0) Not in universe and (99) Unknown, which make up less than 1% of the total sample. We then recoded (11) No, flush toilet to (0) and (21) Flush toilet to (1).

The unique *toilet availability* variable created in two datasets has the categories: (0) No flush toilet and (1) Yes, has a toilet.

- Var4: Bathroom availability

To create the variable for the availability of bathroom facilities we used the variable HH080 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has a proper room with a bath or a shower and it is coded in 2 categories (1) Yes, (2) No. We recoded (2) No as (0).

IPUMS’s BATH variable indicating if the household has access to bathing facilities has the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) No bathing facility, (2) Yes, have bathing facility, exclusivity not specified, (9) Unknown. Universe is defined as private households living in a dwelling. We recoded BATH variable by first dropping the observations with (0) Not in universe and (9) Unknown, which make up less than 1% of the total sample. We then recoded (1) No bathing facility as (0) and (2) Yes, have bathing facility as (1).

The unique *bathroom availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No bathing facility and (1) Yes, with a bathing facility.

- Var5: Telephone availability

From SILC, we used the HS070 variable to create the phone availability variable. In the variable HS070 ‘Do you have a telephone (including mobile phone)?’ is asked and it has 3 categories: (1) Yes, (2) No, but would like to have it but cannot afford, (3) No, not have one for other reasons, e.g. do not want or do not need. We recoded HH070 variable by pooling (2) No, cannot afford and (3) No, other reasons under the category (0) No.

The variable we used for the IPUMS data (PHONE) indicates whether there is at least one active fixed telephone line in the dwelling. However, no further information is provided for mobile phones. No information is provided regarding the reason for not having a telephone either (lack of resources or do not want to have a phone for other reasons). It is coded as (0) Not in universe, (1) No, (2) Yes and (9) Unknown/missing. Universe is defined as private households. We recoded PHONE variable by first dropping the observations with (0) Not in universe and (9) Unknown/missing, which make up less than 1% of the total sample. We then recoded (1) No as (0) and (2) Yes as (1).

The unique *telephone availability* is coded as: (0) No and (1) Yes.

- Var6: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (0) Pre-primary education, (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. Persons who have never been to the education (illiterates) are coded as (-2) in the flag variable. We recoded PE040 by aggregating individuals with Pre-primary education with the persons who have never been to education (which could be identified using the flag variable) and individuals younger than 16, under the category (0) Less than primary.

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which also indicates the highest level of schooling completed. Universe for this variable is defined as persons aged 6 and older in Italy. It has these following categories: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (20) Primary (first stage of basic education), (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed. We recoded EDATTAIN variable by aggregating Less than primary and individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) Less than primary. We recoded Primary (first stage of basic education) as (1) Primary education, Lower secondary (second stage of basic education) as (2) Lower secondary education, Upper secondary as (3) Upper secondary education, Post-secondary non-tertiary as (4) Post-secondary education and University completed as (5) Tertiary education.

The unique *education* variable in two datasets has these categories: (0) Less than primary education (which includes individuals with only pre-primary education, individuals who have never been to education and all the individuals younger than 16), (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) Tertiary education.

- Var7: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person. We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable to create the employment variable with the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed, (3) Inactive. Universe of this variable is individuals 15 and over in Italy. We recoded EMPSTAT variable by gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

We chose to exclude the households with negative equivalised disposable income from our calculations, which led us to drop around 0.5% of the total sample in Italy.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets.

The model we fitted for Italy is:

Income ~ Phone availability + Number of rooms + Tenure status + Toilet availability + Bathroom availability + Education + Employment

For Italy in 2001, we have regional detail at NUTS-2 level in the IPUMS data (19 regions). But the SILC data has no geographical identifier at NUTS-2 level. SILC provides us only with NUTS-1 level geographical identifiers. Therefore, due to this lack of geographical detail at NUTS-2 level in SILC data, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.10 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-2 regions in Italy, year 2004

Region	H	P	G
Piemonte/Valle d'Aosta	0.26	0.07	0.35
Liguria	0.25	0.07	0.35
Lombardia	0.24	0.07	0.35
Bolzano-Bozen/Trento	0.23	0.06	0.34
Veneto	0.22	0.06	0.34
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	0.23	0.06	0.34
Emilia-Romagna	0.24	0.07	0.35
Toscana	0.23	0.07	0.35
Umbria	0.23	0.07	0.35
Marche	0.23	0.06	0.35
Lazio	0.24	0.07	0.35
Abruzzo	0.24	0.07	0.35
Molise	0.25	0.07	0.35
Campania	0.29	0.09	0.35
Puglia	0.27	0.08	0.35
Basilicata	0.27	0.08	0.35
Calabria	0.27	0.08	0.35
Sicilia	0.28	0.08	0.35
Sardegna	0.25	0.07	0.35

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.24 Italian NUTS-2 regions

Source: <https://www.maps4office.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/Italy-Italia-NUTS-2-Map.png>

Figure 3.25 Headcount ratio estimates for Italian regions, year 2004

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.26 Poverty Gap estimates for Italian regions, year 2004

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.27 Gini coefficient estimates for Italian regions, year 2004

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.8 Slovenia

Data sources: Census year 2002, EU-SILC year 2005.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. Only rooms at least 6 square meters were counted with no other restrictions. Therefore, we are not able to identify if kitchens are included or not. This variable is coded as: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms, (6) Six or more rooms and (98) Unknown. Universe is defined as all households. We dropped the unknown observations (less than 0.2% of the total sample).

The unique *number of rooms* variable in two datasets has the categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var2: Toilet availability

We used HH090 from the SILC data to create the variable regarding the availability of toilet. HH090 asks the question: 'Is there an indoor flushing toilet for sole use of the household?' and the answers are coded under two categories: (1) Yes and (2) No. We recoded this variable by changing (2) No to (0).

The variable for the presence of a toilet in the household (TOILET) in the IPUMS data distinguishes between the absence and presence of a flushing toilet and has these categories: (10) No toilet, (21) Flush toilet, (23) Non-flush, other and unspecified. However, no specification is made regarding the exclusivity of access to the toilet facilities. Universe is defined as private occupied dwellings with people present. We recoded (21) Flush toilet as (1) and pooled together (10) No toilet and (23) Non-flush, other and unspecified under the category (0) to refer to 'No flush toilet'. The unique *toilet availability* variable created in two datasets has the categories: (0) No flush toilet and (1) Yes, has a flush toilet.

- Var3: Bathroom availability

To create the variable for the availability of bathroom facilities we used the variable HH080 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has a proper room with a bath or a shower and it is coded in 2 categories (1) Yes, (2) No. We recoded (2) No as (0).

IPUMS's BATH variable indicating if the household has access to bathing facilities has the categories: (1) No bathing facility, (2) Have bathing facility, exclusivity not specified. Universe is defined as all households. We recoded (1) No bathing facility as (0) and (2) Have bathing facility as (1).

The unique *bathroom availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No bathing facility and (1) Yes, with a bathing facility.

- Var4: Telephone availability

From SILC we used the HS070 variable to create the phone availability variable. In the variable HS070 'Do you have a telephone (including mobile phone)?' is asked and it has the categories: (1) Yes, (2) No, but would like to have it but cannot afford. We recoded (2) No, cannot afford as (0) No.

The variable we used for the IPUMS data (PHONE) indicates whether there is a telephone in the dwelling (connection to telephone network). However, no further information is provided for mobile phones. No information is provided regarding the reason for not having a telephone either

(lack of resources or do not want to have a phone for other reasons). It is coded as (1) No and (2) Yes. Universe is defined as all households. We recoded (1) No as (0) and (2) Yes as (1). The unique *telephone availability* is coded as: (0) No and (1) Yes.

- Var5: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (0) Pre-primary education, (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. Persons who have never been to the education (illiterates) are coded as (-2) in the flag variable. We created a wider category by pooling together individuals with Pre-primary education, Primary education and Lower secondary education together with the persons who have never been to education under the category (1) referring to 'Less than Upper secondary education'. We recoded Upper secondary education as (2), Post-secondary education as (3) and Tertiary education as (4). We grouped individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which also indicates the highest level of schooling completed. Universe for this variable is defined as persons aged 15 and older in Slovenia. It has these following categories: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed and (99) Unknown/missing. Individuals with less than basic education (which is 8 years of schooling) are under the code (10) Less than Primary. Individuals who have completed 8 years of schooling are under Lower Secondary and hence it is not possible to identify Primary Education. We first dropped the unknown/missing observations (Less than 0.1% of the total observations). We recoded this variable by aggregating Less than Primary and Lower Secondary education under the new category (1) referring to 'Less than Upper secondary education'. We recoded Upper secondary as (2), Post-secondary as (3) and University completed as (5). Individuals younger than 16 are grouped under the category (0) in line with the education variable we created in SILC.

The unique *education* variable in two datasets has these categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16, (1) Less than Upper Secondary education, (2) Upper secondary education, (3) Post-secondary education, (4) University education.

- Var6: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person. We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable to create the employment variable with the categories: (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive. Universe of this variable is all persons in Slovenia. We recoded EMPSTAT variable by gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

We chose to exclude the households with negative equivalised disposable income from our calculations, which led us to drop around 0.03% of the total sample in Slovenia.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets.

The model we fitted for Slovenia is:

Income ~ Number of rooms + Toilet availability + Bathroom availability + Phone availability + Education + Employment

For Slovenia in 2002, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (13 regions). Due to lack of geographical detail at NUTS-3 level in SILC data, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.11 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Slovenia, year 2005

NUTS-3 Region	H	P	G
Pomurska	0.169	0.045	0.243
Podravska	0.178	0.048	0.246
Koroška	0.168	0.044	0.243
Savinjska	0.174	0.046	0.243
Zasavska	0.200	0.055	0.249
Spodnje-posavska	0.172	0.045	0.242
Jugovzhodna Slovenija	0.173	0.045	0.242
Notranjsko-krška	0.154	0.038	0.238
Osrednjeslovenska	0.145	0.036	0.240
Gorenjska	0.155	0.039	0.240
Goriska	0.151	0.037	0.238
Obalno-krška	0.148	0.036	0.238

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.28 Slovenian NUTS-3 regions

Source: https://simple.wikipedia.org/wiki/Statistical_regions_of_Slovenia

Figure 3.29 Headcount ratio estimates for Slovenian regions, year 2005

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.30 Poverty Gap estimates for Slovenian regions, year 2005

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.31 Gini coefficient estimates for Slovenian regions, year 2005

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.9 Switzerland

Data sources: Census year 2000, EU-SILC year 2008.

Chosen link variables

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. In the IPUMS data, kitchens are also excluded in Switzerland in 2000. This variable is coded from (1) to (15) indicating the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit and (99) Not in universe. Universe is defined as private households and occupied buildings except emergency shelters. We dropped the observations (99) Not in universe (Around 6% of the total sample) and pooled together observations greater than 6 (including 6) in the new category (6) referring to 'Six or more rooms'.

The unique *number of rooms* variable in two datasets has the categories: (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var2: Tenure status

We used HH020 which shows the tenure status of the household with the categories: (1) Owner, (2) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (3) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate (lower price than the market price), (4) Accommodation is provided free. An individual is considered as owner if he possesses a title deed even if the house is fully paid or not. We recoded HH020 pooling together (2) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (3) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate (lower price than the market price), (4) Accommodation is provided free, under the category (0) referring to 'Not owned'.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for tenure status with the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Owned and (2) Not owned. Universe is defined as private households except emergency shelters. Household with mortgage payments are considered as owning the dwelling even if they have not completed all the repayments. We dropped the observations with (0) Not in universe (Around 6% of the total sample) and recoded (2) Not owned to (0).

The final *tenure status* variable we created in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var3: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person. We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable to create the employment variable with the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed, (3) Inactive. Universe of this variable is individuals 15 and over in Switzerland. We recoded EMPSTAT variable by gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

Switzerland 2000 census data provides us with limited number variables. And in the case of education, we needed more clarification since this variable is coded in a different way in Switzerland. It is not possible to identify completion of primary or secondary school since individuals who have

completed mandatory schooling are classified as 'Secondary completed'. On the other hand, individuals who have completed trade school, apprenticeships etc. are recorded having secondary technical degree and individuals with higher professional school degree are recorded as having post-secondary technical education. EDATTAIN variable has these categories in Switzerland: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (40) Upper secondary, (50) Post-secondary non-tertiary, (60) University completed.

We chose to exclude the households with negative equivalised disposable income from our calculations, which led us to drop around 0.2% of the total sample in Switzerland.

Hence, in Switzerland we used only three links variables. The model we fitted for Switzerland is: Income ~ Number of rooms + Tenure status + Employment

For Switzerland in 2000, we have regional detail at NUTS-3 level in the IPUMS data (25 regions). Due to lack of geographical detail in SILC data, we used synthetic estimation fitting a linear model to the data.

Results

Table 3.12 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-3 regions in Switzerland, year 2008

NUTS-3 Region	H	P	G
Vaud	0.245	0.119	0.354
Valais	0.226	0.107	0.345
Geneva	0.259	0.128	0.359
Bern	0.235	0.113	0.349
Freiburg	0.228	0.108	0.347
Solothurn	0.222	0.105	0.344
Neuchatel	0.244	0.118	0.353
Jura	0.221	0.104	0.344
Basel-Stadt	0.270	0.134	0.362
Basel-Landschaft	0.229	0.109	0.348
Aargau	0.220	0.104	0.343
Zurich	0.244	0.118	0.353
Glarus	0.217	0.102	0.342
Schaffhausen	0.226	0.107	0.346
Appenzell Ausserrhoden/Appenzell Innerrhoden	0.214	0.100	0.341
St. Gallen	0.222	0.105	0.344
Graubundun	0.228	0.108	0.346
Thurgau	0.218	0.102	0.342
Luzern	0.230	0.110	0.347
Uri	0.218	0.102	0.342
Schwyz	0.223	0.105	0.344
Obwalden	0.216	0.102	0.342
Nidwalden	0.228	0.109	0.346
Zug	0.235	0.112	0.349
Ticino	0.240	0.116	0.351

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.32 Swiss NUTS-3 regions

Source: <https://gist.github.com/>

Figure 3.33 Headcount ratio estimates for Swiss regions, year 2008

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.34 Poverty Gap estimates for Swiss regions, year 2008

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.35 Gini coefficient estimates for Swiss regions, year 2008

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

3.10 France

Data sources: Census year 2011, EU-SILC year 2011

Chosen link variables:

- Var1: Number of rooms

We used HH030 to create this variable from SILC. HH030 is asked at the household level and indicates the number of rooms available to the household. It is coded as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms. Kitchens are excluded, counted only if cooking activities are in a room used for other purposes.

From IPUMS, we used the variable ROOMS which gives us the number of rooms occupied by the housing unit. Kitchens are included if more than twelve square meters. It is coded from (1) to (20) to indicate the exact number of rooms occupied and (99) which refers to the observations not in universe. No universe description is provided. We dropped these observations which constitute around 2% of the total sample. We pooled together observations greater than six (including six) and coded as (6) to refer to 'Six or more rooms'.

The unique *number of rooms* variable has the following categories: as (1) One room, (2) Two rooms, (3) Three rooms, (4) Four rooms, (5) Five rooms and (6) Six or more rooms.

- Var2: Tenure status

We used HH021 which shows the tenure status of the household with these categories: (1) Outright owner, (2) Owner paying mortgage, (3) Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, (4) Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate, (5) Accommodation is provided free. We

merged the categories (1) Outright owner and (2) Owner paying mortgage of the HH021 variable and recoded it as (1) referring to being an ‘Owner’ and recoded all the rest of the categories (Tenant or subtenant paying rent at prevailing or market rate, Accommodation is rented at a reduced rate and Accommodation is provided free) as (0) referring to ‘Not owner’.

IPUMS has a variable named OWNERSHIP for the tenure status which only distinguishes between (1) Owned and (2) Not owned and has the category (0) to refer to ‘not in universe’. Universe is defined as conventional dwellings. Households with mortgage payments or with other lending arrangements are considered as owning the dwelling even if they have not completed all the repayments. We dropped the observations not in the universe from the sample and recoded ‘Not owned’ as (0).

The unique *tenure status* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) Not owned and (1) Owned.

- Var4: Car availability

To create the variable for car availability, we used the variable HS110 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has a car or not and if not whether because it cannot afford it or for other reasons. It is coded in 3 categories (1) Yes (2) No, cannot afford it (3) No, other reason. Motorcycles and cars or vans provided only for professional purpose are excluded. We pooled together No (cannot afford) and No (other reason) together and recoded as (0) No, without specifying the reason for not owning one to make it compatible with IPUMS.

IPUMS’s AUTOS variable indicates whether a member of the household owned or had use of a vehicle and has these categories: (0) No autos, (1) One auto, (2) Two autos, (3) Three or more autos and (9) Not in universe. Universe is defined as private households. AUTOS variable does not provide us information regarding the reasons for not owning a car (whether because cannot afford or for other reasons e.g. do not need) but provides information regarding the number of cars owned by the household. Cars or vans exclusively for professional use are excluded in the French sample as well. We first dropped the observations ‘Not in universe’. In order to make it compatible with SILC (HS110 does not provide information about the number of cars owned), we pooled together the categories (1) One auto, (2) Two autos, (3) Three or more autos and recoded as (1) referring to ‘Yes, has a car’.

The unique *car availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No, does not have a car and (1) Yes, has a car.

- Var4: Bathroom availability

To create the variable for the availability of bathroom facilities, we used the variable HH081 from SILC. This variable shows if the household has proper room with a bath or a shower and it is coded in 3 categories (1) Yes, for sole use of the household, (2) Shared, (3) No. We recoded (3) No as (0) and pooled together (1) Yes, for sole use of the household and (2) Yes, shared under the category (1) referring to ‘Yes’.

IPUMS’s BATH variable indicates whether the household has access to bathing facilities and has these categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) No bathing facility, (2) Yes, have bathing facility, exclusivity not specified. After dropping the observations ‘Not in universe’, we recoded (1) No bathing facility as (0) and (2) Yes, have bathing facility as (1).

The unique *bathroom availability* variable in two datasets has the categories: (0) No bathing facility and (1) Yes, with a bathing facility.

- Var3: Education

For education, we use the variable PE040 (Highest ISCED level attained) from SILC, which is available for all current household members aged 16 and over. PE040 has the categories: (0) Pre-primary education, (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education, (4) Post-secondary education, (5) First stage of tertiary education (not leading directly to an advanced research qualification) and second stage of tertiary education (leading to an advanced

research qualification). Persons who have not completed their studies are coded according to the highest level they have completed. We pooled individuals younger than 16 together with individuals with pre-primary education under the category (0). We recoded Post-secondary education as (3) and Tertiary education as (4).

We used the EDATTAIN variable from the IPUMS data which indicates the highest level of schooling completed. The universe for this variable is defined as persons aged 14 and older. It has these following categories: (0) Not in the universe, (10) Less than primary, (20) Primary (first stage of basic education), (30) Lower secondary (second stage of basic education), (40) Upper secondary and (60) University completed. We pooled all the individuals younger than 16 together with individuals with Less than primary education under the category (0). We recoded Primary education as (1), Lower secondary education as (2), Upper secondary as (3) and University completed as (4).

Education variable common to two datasets has the categories: (0) Individuals younger than 16 and with less than primary education, (1) Primary education, (2) Lower secondary education, (3) Upper secondary education and (4) University.

- Var4: Employment

We used RB210 (Basic activity status) variable from SILC to create the employment variable, which is asked for all current household members of any age. RB210 has these categories: (1) At work, (2) Unemployed, (3) In retirement or early retirement, (4) Other inactive person. We recoded RB210 variable in SILC data by pooling (3) In retirement or early retirement and (4) Other inactive person under (3) Inactive. We also pooled individuals younger than 16 under the category (0).

From IPUMS, we used EMPSTAT variable, which has the categories: (0) Not in universe, (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive. The universe of this variable is individuals 14 and over. We recoded EMPSTAT variable in the IPUMS data, gathering individuals younger than 16 under the category (0) as well.

New *employment* variable has these categories: (0) Not in universe (individuals younger than 16), (1) Employed, (2) Unemployed and (3) Inactive.

We chose to exclude the households with negative equivalised disposable income from our calculations, which led us to drop around 0.07% of the total sample in France.

After having created the link variables, we constructed the formula to use in the EBP analysis; with all the link variables coded exactly the same in both datasets:

$\text{Income} \sim \text{Number of rooms} + \text{Tenure status} + \text{Bathroom availability} + \text{Car availability} + \text{Education} + \text{Employment}$

For France in 2011, we have geographical detail at NUTS-2 level both in IPUMS and SILC. While IPUMS has 26 NUTS-2 regions, SILC covers only 22 NUTS-2 regions (excludes the overseas departments of France like Guadeloupe, Martinique, Guyane and Reunion). We fit a mixed model and produce estimates for these out-of-sample units as well.

Results

Table 3.13 Table with values of H (Headcount ratio), P (Poverty Gap) and G (Gini coefficient) for the NUTS-2 regions in France, year 2011

NUTS-2 Region	H	P	G
Region d'Île de France	0.139	0.043	0.297
Champagne-Ardenne	0.235	0.083	0.313
Picardie	0.240	0.085	0.314
Haute-Normandie	0.231	0.081	0.313
Centre	0.211	0.072	0.307
Basse-Normandie	0.223	0.077	0.310
Bourgogne	0.221	0.077	0.309
Nord-Pas-de-Calais	0.270	0.099	0.322
Lorraine	0.226	0.079	0.311
Alsace	0.222	0.078	0.312
Franche-Comté	0.208	0.071	0.307
Pays de la Loire	0.204	0.069	0.304
Bretagne	0.208	0.071	0.305
Poitou-Charentes	0.217	0.074	0.306
Aquitaine	0.209	0.071	0.306
Midi-Pyrénées	0.210	0.071	0.306
Limousin	0.280	0.103	0.320
Rhône-Alpes	0.182	0.060	0.302
Auvergne	0.241	0.085	0.312
Languedoc-Roussillon	0.225	0.078	0.310
Provence-Alpes-Côte d'Azur	0.221	0.076	0.310
Corse	0.254	0.091	0.314
Guadeloupe	0.254	0.091	0.315
Martinique	0.272	0.099	0.318
Guyane	0.356	0.143	0.341
Réunion	0.279	0.103	0.321

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Maps

Figure 3.36 French NUTS-2 regions

Source: <http://www.map-france.com/regions/>

Figure 3.37 Headcount ratio estimates for French regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.38 Poverty Gap estimates for French regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data

Figure 3.39 Gini coefficient estimates for French regions, year 2011

Source: Own elaboration based on IPUMS and EU-SILC data.

4. Concluding remarks and future challenges

In this report, we have presented poverty and inequality indicators across European regions covering the highest geographical precision that the available census and household survey data permitted, for as many countries as possible. The EBP approach used in this report is the state-of-the-art methodology currently used in small area estimation.

It would have been desirable that household survey data were geo-referenced at the same level as the censuses in order for the EBP method to work at its maximal potential. Unfortunately, such level of detail has been unobtainable in many cases. To our surprise, the geographic detail of the EU-SILC data has been much poorer than initially expected (see Table 3.3). In order to overcome this problem, we have requested EUROSTAT to provide more geographic detail of the surveyed households (i.e. determine the NUTS-3 regions where the households belong) - without success. Because of statistical confidentiality reasons, the access to the requested information has not been facilitated.

Given the lack of geographical precision, we have resorted to the so-called synthetic estimators as a fallback plan. Essentially, this means that the fixed-effects coefficients that the EBP method aims to estimate for each small area (typically at NUTS-3 level) are assumed to be constant within each region higher in the hierarchy (i.e. so that all NUTS-3 fixed effect coefficients within a given NUTS-2 region are assumed to be the same - see equation (4) in the Appendix). While this reduces the precision of our estimates, it is the best one can do given the existing data access limitations.

One of the consequences of synthetic estimation is that the variability of our regional estimates is substantially reduced. Failure to identify the ‘small areas’ (at NUTS-3 level) where the household survey observations belong does not allow capturing the regional variability patterns appropriately, therefore resulting in excessively uniform distributions. From our experience, in order to improve the precision of our estimates in future work, it would be necessary to have (i) higher geographic detail of household survey information, and/or (ii) larger census sample sizes - ideally both. With both conditions met, our small area poverty and inequality estimates would be more precise and reliable.

appendix 1 Technical Appendix: methodology: small area estimation of poverty indicators using the nested error regression model

In a seminal paper, Elbers *et al.* (2003) proposed a methodology for estimating poverty indicators at the small area level. The methodology consists of a nested error regression (random effects) model with cluster random effects that is estimated by using survey data. The response variable, which is not available in the Census, is the logarithm of a welfare variable, e.g. income or consumption, and the explanatory variables, used for modeling the welfare variable, is available both in the survey and in the Census datasets. Once the model has been estimated using the survey data, the estimated model parameters are combined with Census microdata to form unit level synthetic Census predictions of the welfare variable. The synthetic values of income/consumption alongside a defined poverty line are then used for estimating deprivation indicators for example, the incidence of poverty (HCR), the poverty gap (PG) and the poverty severity (Foster *et al.*, 1984). Routinely we refer to this poverty mapping methodology as the World Bank (WB) approach.

More recently, Molina and Rao (2010) proposed an Empirical Best Prediction (EBP) approach for estimating poverty indicators at the small area level, which is similar to the WB approach but generates Census predictions of income/consumption by using the conditional predictive distribution of the out of sample data given the sample data. Molina and Rao (2010) demonstrated the superior performance of the EBP approach, when compared to the WB approach, under the nested error regression model.

In this appendix, we review in more detail how these different approaches are defined.

Notation and definitions

In what follows we assume that a vector of p auxiliary variables \mathbf{x}_{ij} is known for each population unit i in small area $j = 1, \dots, m$ and that values of the welfare variable of interest y_{ij} are available from a random sample, s , that includes units from all the small areas of interest. We denote the population size, sample size, sampled part of the population and non-sampled part of the population in area j respectively by N_j , n_j , s_j , r_j . We assume that the sum over the areas of N_j and n_j is equal to N and n respectively. We further assume that conditional on covariate information, for example design variables, the sampling design is ignorable.

All poverty mapping methods we describe in this deliverable assume the availability of survey data on a welfare variable (income/consumption) and explanatory variables that can be used for modelling the outcome variable. In addition, the methods assume the availability of Census/administrative data on the same set of explanatory variables. Some methods further assume that the Census and survey data are linked. However, this assumption is fairly unrealistic as in most cases the link between the survey and the Census data is not known. Finally, the methods that are based on the nested error regression model (WB and EBP) conventionally use a logarithmic transformation of the welfare variable. Nevertheless, before proceeding to small area estimation, it is always advisable to use model diagnostics because a logarithmic transformation may not be the optimal one. In this report we focus on the estimation of HCR and PG as defined by Foster *et al.* (1984) and on the estimation of the Gini

coefficient. Denoting by t the poverty line, different poverty indicators are defined by the area-specific mean of the derived variable

$$z_{ij}(\alpha, t) = \left(\frac{t - y_{ij}}{t} \right)^\alpha I(y_{ij} \leq t), \quad i = 1, \dots, N_j.$$

Setting $\alpha = 0$ defines the HCR in small area j , $z_j(0, t)$, which is the mean of $z_{ij}(0, t)$. Similarly, setting $\alpha = 1$ defines the G in small area j , $z_j(1, t)$, which is the mean of $z_{ij}(1, t)$.

The WB method

The most widely used method for small area poverty mapping is the so-called WB method (Elbers *et al.*, 2003). In its simplest form and assuming a non-informative sampling design, the WB method assumes a nested error regression model on the logarithmically transformed values of y_{ij} ,

$$y_{ij} = \mathbf{x}_{ij}\boldsymbol{\beta}^T + u_j + \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad u_j \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2), \quad \varepsilon_{ij} \sim N(0, \sigma_\varepsilon^2). \quad (1)$$

The WB method starts by estimating (1) using the sample data. Once estimates of the fixed effects, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}$, of the variance components, $\hat{\sigma}_u^2$, $\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2$, and of the area random effects \hat{u}_j have been obtained, the WB method uses the following bootstrap population model for generating L synthetic Censuses, $y_{ij}^* = \mathbf{x}_{ij}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^T + u_j^* + \varepsilon_{ij}^*$, $u_j^* \sim N(0, \hat{\sigma}_u^2)$, $\varepsilon_{ij}^* \sim N(0, \hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2)$.

The exact steps of the Monte-Carlo simulation are as follows. Start by estimating (1) using the sample data; draw L population vectors of y_{ij}^* using (2); Using the synthetic values of the welfare variable, y_{ij}^* , compute the WB estimate from the l^{th} synthetic Census, $\hat{z}_j^{*WB(l)}(\alpha, t)$; average the results over L Monte Carlo simulations.

Using the bootstrap population model (2), one can further compute the MSE of the estimated poverty indicators,

$$\text{MSE} \left[\hat{z}_j^{*WB}(\alpha, t) \right] = L^{-1} \sum_{l=1}^L \left[\hat{z}_j^{*WB(l)}(\alpha, t) - E \left(\hat{z}_j^{*WB}(\alpha, t) \right) \right]^2.$$

One distinct aspect of the WB method is that the random effect is specified at the cluster (e.g. primary sampling units) level and not necessarily at the level of the target small area. This is in contrast to the alternative methodologies we describe later on in this deliverable. To simplify things, for the purposes of this report we assume that clusters and target small areas coincide. As Molina and Rao (2010)

pointed out, when small areas and clusters coincide and since $E(u_j^*) = 0$, $E(\varepsilon_{ij}^*) = 0$, in the simplest case of estimating a small area mean, and denoting by U_j the population of units in domain j ,

the WB method leads to $E(y_{ij}^*) = N_j^{-1} \sum_{k \in U_j} \mathbf{x}_{kj}\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}^T$, which is a regression synthetic estimator. It

may be reasonable to assume that in many cases a regression synthetic estimator will be less efficient than competing indirect estimators.

The EBP method

The EBP method was proposed by Molina and Rao (2010). Like the WB approach, the EBP approach also relies on the use of a nested error regression model on the logarithmically transformed welfare variable. Let us start the description of the method by decomposing the population small area-specific poverty indicator as follows,

$$z_j(\alpha, t) = N_j^{-1} \left[\sum_{i \in s_j} z_i(\alpha, t) + \sum_{k \in r_j} z_k(\alpha, t) \right]. \quad (3)$$

The first component in (3) is observed in the sample whereas the second component is unknown and should be estimated by using a small area model, which is estimated with the sample data. Similarly to the WB method, the EBP method starts by estimating the nested error regression model to obtain estimates of the fixed effects, $\hat{\beta}$, of the variance components, $\hat{\sigma}_u^2$, $\hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2$, and of the area random effects \hat{u}_j .

The EBP method then simulates out of sample data from the conditional distribution of the out of sample data given the sample data. This is done by using the following bootstrap population model for generating L synthetic Censuses:

$$y_{ij}^* = \mathbf{x}_{ij} \hat{\beta}^T + \hat{u}_j + u_j^* + \varepsilon_{ij}^*, u_j^* \sim N\left(0, \hat{\sigma}_u^2(1 - \gamma_j)\right), \varepsilon_{ij}^* \sim N\left(0, \hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2\right), \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma_j = \frac{\hat{\sigma}_u^2}{\left(\hat{\sigma}_u^2 + \hat{\sigma}_\varepsilon^2 / n_j\right)}.$$

The exact steps of the Monte-Carlo simulation are as follows. Start by estimating (1) using the sample data; draw L out of sample vectors of y_{ij}^* using (4); combine the sample y_{ij} with the out of sample y_{ij}^* values; compute the EBP estimate for the l^{th} synthetic Census, $\hat{z}_j^{\text{EBP}(l)}(\alpha, t)$; average the results over L Monte Carlo simulations. Focusing again on the simplest case of estimating a small area mean and since $E(u_j^*) = 0, E(\varepsilon_{ij}^*) = 0$, the EBP approach leads to

$$E(y_{ij}^*) = N_j^{-1} \left[\sum_{i \in s_j} y_i + \sum_{k \in r_j} \mathbf{x}_{kj} \hat{\beta}^T + \hat{u}_j \right],$$

which is expected to be more efficient than the regression synthetic estimates obtained with the WB approach.

MSE estimation for the EBP estimates relies on a parametric bootstrap scheme (see also Gonzalez-Manteiga *et al.*, 2008). In particular, using the bootstrap population model (2) B bootstrap populations are generated and the target population parameters are computed for each bootstrap population. From each bootstrap population a sample is selected and the EBP approach is implemented using the sample and bootstrap population data. MSE estimates of the EBP estimates are computed over the B bootstrap replications.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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